

Performance Based Neural Network Distribution for IOT Devices Deployment

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Abstract: Neural network decomposition is an emerging research area aimed at improving the efficiency of neural networks, especially as data volumes and network complexities increase. The need for decomposition grows as it helps reduce latency and optimize the use of computational resources, particularly in low-capacity IoT devices. This decomposition process is essential for enhancing the performance of neural networks when deployed in resource-constrained environments. Co-design, which integrates both software and hardware, plays a key role in this context by offering a framework for efficient decomposition. In our proposed approach, we focus on decomposing a fully connected neural network to address issues such as computational power loss, communication latency, and data transfer costs typically associated with centralized processing. We implemented this decomposition using Python and multi-threading techniques, modeling IoT devices in a given system. Our results demonstrated the feasibility of decomposing fully connected neural networks, making it possible to run them on small, low-power devices without significant performance degradation. These promising findings suggest that our decomposition technique can optimize neural networks for IoT applications. Future work will involve applying this method to other neural network architectures and types, exploring its potential for a wider range of use cases and ensuring scalability and efficiency across various IoT systems. This will pave the way for more effective deployment of deep learning models on resource-constrained devices.

Keywords: Neural Network, Neural Network distribution, Neural Network Performance, Co-Design, Internet of Things Infrastructure

1. INTRODUCTION

Like every research issue, our proposed approach is not unique, and many different researches are dealing with such targeted systems. In the aforementioned works, researchers are dealing with the neural network distribution over the IoT components. Generally, results are promising and imported technique enhancement, but like every research file, perfection is impossible which means previous works have all a weakness points in their proposed distributed system. Generally speaking, decomposition appears like very important and fundamental for a lot of scientific fields [1]. From this stage, we propose a decomposition technique which can overcome challenges faced in some previous works like the bottleneck caused by the computing insufficiency. Our proposed methodology is designed first to face the distribution problem which come just after the problem of processing decentralization. This methodology is leading us toward the fully deployment of the IoT objects, avoid the computer power insufficiency, reducing the centralized processing charge and complexity and minimize the vertical communication cost in time and energy.

2. PRELIMINARIES

This section provides the concepts of artificial neural networks, different architectures and principles, the GENETIC ALGORITHMS and the MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION ANALYSIS.

A. Artificial Intelligence

Sometimes called machine intelligence, mimics the cognitive function which was traditionally associated to the human brain [2]. We consider a smart object any device that perceives its environment and takes actions that maximize its chance of successfully achieving its goals. It is kind of intelligence ensured by machines dedicated to solve problems of high level complexity, which classical programming cannot deal with [3]. While dealing with basic IoT system based on small devices transmitting raw data to a central server for simple applications, nowadays system are increasingly complex, dealing with bigger applications and making more complex decision [4]. For better performance, optimization in energy, time and memory, Artificial Intelligence which has proved its utility in such situation took place in these IoT systems. AI basic techniques are machine learning and neural networks.

1) Artificial Neural Network

Neural Networks are used to address nonlinear regression analysis problems [5]. It has been proved that a neural network with only one hidden layer can simulate very complex nonlinear functions. Neural networks are a part of the previous techniques, neural networks were inspired from natural brain neural networks, in which neuron series trigger and stimulate a response. Inputs directed to a central unit called neuron for an activation function (the processing function) ended by output as described in 1, this last which can be divided into multiple direction depending on its location and specific function in the network. This last is composed of multiple interconnected neurons.

Figure 1. BASIC NEURON FUNCTION DESCRIPTION

a) Artificial Neural Network distribution
low low low low low

2) GENETIC ALGORITHMS

Machine learning is one of the keys means of IoT [6] which provides information inference and IoT devices intelligence. It is considered as a promising solution in lot of IoT application domains. It aims to create model based on observation and experiences and then uses this model to predict future information and makes decisions. This technique can be divided into “Supervised learning”, and “Unsupervised learning”, “Reinforcement learning”. Where its use is divided between three application within which we have “classification”, “regression”, “clustering” . Machine learning is one of the most appropriate computational paradigms to dote IoT devices with intelligence [7]. A very known and most used machine learning algorithm we have the GENETIC ALGORITHMS which is one of the excellent algorithms for solving simple single-objective problems, and the GAs frameworks are used by many researchers as the main body for solving multi-objective problems[8],since it gives a better diversity and convergence than other multi-objective algorithms. The genetic algorithm was introduced in 1971 by John Holland, it is based on a random mechanism of search which are called random solution, and it reflects the theory of biological evolution [9].

Figure 2. BASIC GENETIC ALGORITHM FLOWCHART

A basic genetic algorithm flow chart is given in 2, it shows the main four operation repeated in the GA process. It starts with an initial population which is a randomly generated population, secondly, the objective function is applied on every individual on the generated population. ones the fitness (the objective function result) is calculated, a selection process starts ans select the best portion of the population. here comes the crossover process to generate a new population based on the selected portion and it ends with some individual values modification under the name of mutation process.

B. INTERNET OF THINGS IOT

1) DEFINITION

Even when the world is dealing with the Internet of Things concepts for a long time, many organizations gave definitions of it [10]. Then it has no specific definition in hand. We have the semantic definition which says that IoT is a world-wide network of interconnected things which can be addressed anywhere through a standard communication protocols [11]. Where the general definition given in [12] describes the IoT concepts as the identification of connected objects and their representation in the network structure. In [10] according to IEEE, the definition of IOT is divided into two; depending on the complexity of the IoT systems. It is a network that connects uniquely identifiable things to the internet and collect data about it.

Figure 3. Internet of Things Elements.

Their state is editable from anywhere anytime and by anything for simple IoT systems. Where for complex one, the IoT introduce more complex system such the self-reconfigurable; adaptive and complex networks which interconnect objects using standard communication protocols. Things may own physical or virtual representation. Accordingly, discoverable web service on IP network is offered by the devices, then a wrapping layer is needed, which consist of two main sub-layers. The interface layer responsible of the incoming/outcoming operations, and the communication sub-layer which handle the logic behind the web services methods and translate these methods to communicate with the real world.

2) IOT COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES

Communication is an important element of the IOT to transfer data between devices, which is a crucial operation for the efficiency of a IOT project. Besides the word Internet is being an important part of IoT and with the increased use of Sensor Networks and applications in the most diverse environments, not all the situations rely on Internet related protocols and the need of different protocols, both wired and wireless, is growing [13]. The most known wired technologies are Serial Communication or Universal Asynchronous Receiver and Transmitter (UART), mainly in the form of USB or RS232, RS485, SPI, I2C and PLC. Also for networks that need a bigger reliability, CAN bus can be used .

C. MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION ANALYSIS

Decision making process aims to optimize the objective function over a set of multiple feasible solutions, however it is often related to a different viewpoints or criteria [14] which can be conflicting and need to be given due consideration. MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION comes to overcome this challenge, and it consist of four non-linear recursive steps [15]:

- decision problem structuring
- preferences articulation
- alternative evaluation aggregation
- solution recommendations

This process is adopted to deal with the multi-criteria architecture selection in the neural network decomposition technique.

D. PROBLEM FORMULATION

E. Co-Design Concept

Co-design is a hardware software conceptual approaches, for the system on chip implementation. The technique compose three sub-techniques [16], the first software-driven technique. With which the specification of the hardware is defined based on the software resources demands. The second hardware driven technique by which the system optimization is required to make the available resources up to handle the systems complexity. Where the third one is a mixed technique of the two previous ones.

3. PERFORMANCE BASED NEURAL NETWORK DISTRIBUTION

A. Neural Networks Distribution Related Work

The concept of distributing the artificial neural network is not new. Since 1995 [22] proposed the distribution of the neural network learning over multiple computers in the goal of reducing the learning time complexity. The proposed neural network in which the input layer forwards a copy of the input data over the multiple feed-forward neural network blocs. And an output layers with build in winner-takes-all algorithm. An approach which approved its efficiency in term of time complexity. This work is also optimized by an approach of changeable number of blocs depending on the accessible processors [17]. The resulting neural network will be uploaded in one ship device and if the neural network is deep and require memory and processing, it will normally be placed in upper level of the IoT architecture which means less distribution and more communication criteria would be asked. By [18] a framework is proposed for simultaneous data transfer and processing, this framework maps the artificial neural network operation through communication, in the goal of reducing the latency and energy consumption caused by the centralized processing. One hidden layer of neurons are distributed over the IoT mesh network. The principle ideas was placing the hidden neurons near the input and output nodes, avoiding the central gateway and its surrounded nodes. This framework reduced the latency and energy consumption. This work is very promising but real world problems are requiring more than one hidden layer in neural network and for more complicated neural networks and less

Figure 4. PERFORMANCE BASED NEURAL NETWORK DIS- TRIBUTION

devices are connected the proposed framework is somehow limited in this case. As discussed previously, [19] proposed the distribution of a deep neural network over different IoT architecture levels. The DNN is distributed over the cloud, the gate way and the object. This distribution is dotted of exit points for decision making in going to the upper level of make end depending on the result of the processing. It is a very promising road to the distribution techniques but the problem with this technique is the duplication of the same neural network over different objects, things which make the ANN redundant and devices are not fully deployed but one replicated deployment. [20] proposed an architecture dealing with the problem of distributing the neural network and the training data set. Incremental data partitioning and allocation was proposed and also a global weight updating was proposed. This last is dealing with the problem of the heterogeneity of the different components of the target system. In the goal of passing over the problem of the deference between provided computing power of the different components; which has an impact on the time response of each one. The strategy is proposed in a way that eliminating the waiting part of the process and updating weight after every received weight update. The experiments of such technique

showed that the proposed methodology improves the training time and the accuracy of the CNN. The problem is also like the problem with the proposed methodology by [18], that the resulting trained neural network would be uploaded in one chip device and it may cause the centralized processing and high communication cost. Moreover, each node of the neural network is trained with a portion of the dataset, this technique which may make the local weights converge to solve this portion of the dataset and not the whole one. Serial decomposition of neural network is proposed by [23]. Dealing with huge amount of data, instead of working on one big neural network, the tip is to decompose the data set based on heuristics into sub- sets of data and rules. Using the resulting subsets, they works on multiple simple neural network. It is a very powerful decomposition technique which if applied in the IoT domain would enhance the latency and communication cost. But this approach, instead if working on the neural network as a unique block, it applies the functional decomposition based on the dataset decomposition.

TABLE I. Decomposition techniques classification

Works	Artificial Neural Network	Concept	Distribution	Domain	Benefits	Algorithm
[[17]]	Feed forward multi-layered neural network	Learning	Multiprocessing units	Smart car (broketorque)	Time complexity	Winner takes all
[[18]]	One hidden layer neural network	Computing	IoT meshnetwork	Grid topologies (grid parking sensors, spare devices factory plans)	Latency and power consumption	Network as computer
[[19]]	Deep neural network	Computing	IoT physical architecture	Image processing (video surveillance)	Latency and communication requirements	Exit points
[[20]]	Convolutional neural network	Learning	Multiprocessing blocks	Image processing	Time complexity, accuracy and heterogeneity	Global weights updates and incremental data partitioning
[[21]]	Deep neural network	Learning	Computers system	Air pollution measurement of a power plant	Latency and communication costs	Functional decomposition

[Table 1] gives the classification of different distribution and decomposition technique viewed in the literature. Interpreting line per line the given table, gives us the different challenges present in each of the techniques. The common challenge between [17] and [23] was the duplication of the neural network model in the different processing block, resulting the use of the composed computational power for one purpose. Else the computational power is a crucial and important actor for the increasing connectivity and data exchangers, regarding our target system and codesign technique adopted. In addition, the decomposition technique of the dataset will cause the weight local convergence which is specific for the sub dataset and not to the whole dataset. Moreover, the resulting neural network would be definitely huge and complex, than the computational requirements are asked again. In the [18] proposed solution, The network as computer is a powerful decentralized computing,

dealing with one hidden layer neural network. Increasing the number of the neurons in more than one hidden layer would be computation power consumer. More over for less connected devices in the mesh network, the distribution would be critical and result some latency disadvantages. can be more efficient than putting neuron per device. For the convolutional neural network training technique by [20] is a promising time optimizer. But the resulting neural network which required the time optimization is clearly a complex one. Where its deployment is computing power consumer. Exactly as the resulting neural networks by [21] regarding the raw dataset. Even the sub networks are mostly complex. And the weights convergence problem for the partitioned dataset. Since the computing complexity of the neural networks is proposed in different literatures works, and the bottleneck phenomena of the insufficiency of GPU/CPU capacities of the target components. And based on the advantages of the co-design techniques which can help in the computing power collection. We propose a neural network decomposition over different IoT low level physical architecture to benefit from the calculation capacities of these components.

B. PROPOSED SOLUTION

In our solution, we propose an already learned neural network, in which we apply our decomposition technique. The purpose is not the learning but the inference task instead. The technique is composed of two tasks that are, decomposition and performance calculation. In the first stage, based on the neural network architecture (fully connected network in our case), our technique starts the neurons isolation one by one from the first neuron of the input layer until obtaining the best decomposition. The number of sub-networks depends on the available embedded card in the target system. In this stage, the connection type is also selected either WIFI, Bluetooth, or any available connection in the programmable cards. The second stage is the performance study. Once the distribution step is done, and the communication type is selected, a simulation starts and criteria are taken in consideration to select the best distribution. Time response between the sub-networks (two sub-networks in our case), the communication cost depending on the connection type and transferred data, and the processing power required for each sub-network. In one distribution, different performance studies are performed, by which every possible connection type is tested. These two stages are repeated until the best decomposition with the best connection is selected. According to our objective function, the best decomposition is the one with less waiting time between the two chips and adequate memory and processor occupation. The simulation can be performed in an FPGA card, in which communication is faster and optimal, and the fact that the FPGA cards are an important environment designed for the co-design tasks. As shown in the figure 4. A fully connected network is taken as an input for the FPGA card, control systems are embedded like response time control and CPU occupation. Decomposition steps are applied and performance studies are investigated. The output of the card is the optimal decomposition adequate to the available material. Moving from specific application to general model where we can have more than two devices in the target system. In this stage, the distribution methodology is ensured by the adoption of genetic algorithms, [24]. Population would be vectors of size D (D is the number of a given devices in the target system), and the sum of values of each vector equal to the number of neurons in the artificial neural network. The objective functions are the same criteria studied above. The rest of the approach follows the genetic algorithms steps.

One artificial neuron represents a mathematical operation that requires some processing power. In a full architecture with thousands of neurons, the processing power needed becomes important. The equation number 1 gives the mathematical formula of one artificial neuron with a simple transfer function Sigmoid. This processing power is one of the

challenges faced during artificial neural network conception which should be investigated and optimized.

$$output = f(iI \sum w_i x_i + b) \quad (1)$$

where

- x_i : the inputs
- w_i : connections' weights
- b : the bias
- I : inputs' number of the given neuron
- f : the activation function

The Sigmoid transfer is given by the equation 2

$$S(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}} \quad (02)$$

where

- x_x : The sum of weights multiplied by input values

1) Decomposition

The sum operation needs one calculation unit, the multiplication also needs one calculation unit. For an artificial neuron with five (5) valued inputs the operation needs θU unit of time where θU is given in the equation 3

$$\theta U = \underbrace{\ln\left(\frac{5}{6}\right)}_{\text{sum}} \underbrace{\hspace{1.5cm}}_{\text{multiplication}} \quad (3)$$

This calculation requirement is multiplied by thousands depending on the number of neurons in deep neural networks, which means a huge calculation and processing power. This last is not provided in the small devices in IoT low-level objects. This huge neural network needs decomposition, to load it in devices with small capacities that work in collaboration.

$$\theta U = \underbrace{\ln\left(\frac{5}{6}\right)}_{\text{sum}} \underbrace{\hspace{1.5cm}}_{\text{multiplication}} \text{ equation for transfer canals} \quad (4)$$

Transfer canals could be WIFI, Bluetooth, Ethernet depending on the provided connection type in the target device. Transfer cost changes depending on the transfer technique and the transferred data size. This transfer cost is not the only studied criteria, but the speed is taken in consideration too, so that inputs for the next neurons in the second device would be provided as soon as possible. This speed is given in the equation 4.

2) Response Time

Response time is very important in our methodology, because in a artificial neural network inputs of one unit should be simultaneous to avoid latency. In distributed system and in our approach, distributed neural network, latency problem is known as the bottleneck problem which is caused by the heterogeneity of devices and different time of response. as shown in figure 5, the time on the external communication should be reduced as small as possible to avoid this latency problem.

Figure 5. Internal/External Communication Canals

The built-in communication canals and especially in modern devices are faster, compared to external communication techniques, and the selection of the optimal one is one of the studied criteria in our approach. Regarding the size of transferred data between neurons which is small, the communication cost is not important but in case of transferring more than one neuron's output it becomes critical.

3) CPU Occupation

In a neural network architecture thousands of neurons works in parallel, which requires a big calculation power, that means important CPU occupation. For a given neuron to execute the built-in function needs θC processing units, and for transferring data from a neuron to another consumes αT processing unit. For a neural network architecture with two thousand (2000) neurons and four thousand (4000) connections, at least the processing power Pp needed for executing this architecture is in the average of equation 5

$$Pp = (\theta C * 2000) + (\alpha T * 4000) \quad (5)$$

this processing power in not provided in small devices of the low level IoT architectures. From this crucial point, the distribution of the architecture would be the best solution for small devices deployment.

C.IMPLEMENTATION

In this section, the two algorithms for the specific and general case are implemented. The first algorithm for the specific case of two programmable cards summarizes the methodology process. It takes as input the neural network architecture and calculation capabilities of the two target devices. Each step, one neuron is added to the first device and the rest on the neural network is uploaded in the second device. Four (04) metrics are then calculated which are Time response, CPU Occupation, Communication cost and S selection metric. The three first metrics are the input of the fourth metric which is taken as an objective function of our methodology. For each step, metrics are stored in a table with the corresponding architecture, until the end of the distribution process. Once the distribution algorithm is

ended, the metrics table is used to calculate the S selection metric using the multi-criteria decision analysis to get the best obtained decomposition.

For every distribution that is better than the previous best one, this distribution is taken as the best solution. Until the end of the process, these metrics are calculated in a pool. The output is the optimal distributed neural network architecture with the optimal performance.

The second algorithm gives the process flow when we move to general case with more than two devices in the target system. In this case the genetic algorithm is adopted to deal with the distribution task. It takes as input the neural network architecture, devices number as sub-networks count, the population size for the genetic algorithm and the size of the selected population for the next generation. The first step in the algorithm is to generate population which is vectors of size equal to the number of available devices, and the sum of values of each vector equals to the number of neurons in the neural network architecture. Each value in each vector represents the number on neurons in each portion of neural network for each device. Every generation, the population is taken one by one i.e. every vector is treated and the neural network architecture is partitioned depending on the vector values. Same metrics are calculated, moreover the connection types are investigated between every related device.

TABLE II. Neurons Per Devices Decomposition Table

-	Iteration 1	Iteration 2	Iteration 3	Iteration 10	Iteration N
Device 1	1 Neurons	2 Neurons	3 Neurons	10 Neurons	16 Neurons
Device 2	15 Neurons	14 Neurons	13 Neurons	6 Neurons	0 Neurons
Device 1	90 Neurons	10 Neurons	5 Neurons	0 Neurons	55 Neurons
Device 2	50 Neurons	100 Neurons	80 Neurons	110 Neurons	30 Neurons
Device 3	20 Neurons	50 Neurons	75 Neurons	50 Neurons	75 Neurons

Algorithm 2: Algorithm 2

```

1 Input: ANN architecture, D Sub-networks count,
  Processing power of target devices, Population,
  Selection
2 Output: Optimal ANN decomposition
3 Solution ← generate(population)
4 while not end do
5   for i ← 1 to Population do
6     Evaluation ← for_each_individual(P)
      /a_processor_for_a_card)
7   end
8   Selection ← (Evaluation(population))
9   Reproduction ←
    Selection(selected_population)
10  New_population ← Mutation(reproduction)
11  Population ← New_population
12 end
13 Output ← select_Best(Selection)

```

Algorithm 1: Algorithm 1

```

1 Input: ANN architecture, D Sub-networks count
  (O2), Processing power of target devices, N
  neurons count, Global_S, Part1, Part2, CC
  communication canal.
2 Output: Optimal ANN decomposition Sub ← 1
  while not end do
3   for i ← 1 to Sub do
4     D(1) ← allocate_neuron(i, ANN
      architecture)
5   end
6   for j ← Sub + 1 to N do
7     D(2) ← allocate_rest_of_ANN(j, ANN
      architecture)
8   end
9 end
10 T ← time_response(D(1), D(2))
11 Cpu1 ← CPU_occupation(D(1))
12 Cpu2 ← CPU_occupation(D(2))
13 C ← communication(D(1), D(2), avail_connec)
14 S ← calculate(T, Cpu1, Cpu2, C)
15 if S better than Global_S then
16   Global_S ← S
17   Part1 ← D(1)
18   Part2 ← D(2)
19   CC ← C
20 end
21 Sub ← Sub + 1

```

The performance of the distribution for each vector is saved to select the population that is used to generate the future generation. The reproduction would be a cross generation between the selected individuals of the population, and the mutation would be the modification of some vectors values to ensure the correct neurons count. This process is repeated until the end of the given generation count.

D. SIMULATION

1) Simulation Setup

To prove the efficiency of our methodology, a simulation was conducted on an intel(R) Core(TM)i7-8550U HP-CPU with 16GB RAM, using Visual Studio 2019 Python 3.0 neural network script. The choice of Python language is justified with the objective of easily manipulate and treat neural network architectures. An already trained fully connected neural network architecture is used, which means the learning task is not taken in consideration but the inference instead. The decomposition on the multi-devices distributions is simulated with threads. communication cost is not studied, since our simulation is done in one machine with multiple threads. the dataset used in our learning process is randomly generated data of 4 features inputs and 3 features output, adequately to our neural network architecture of [4,5,4,3] for the first scenario of two provided devices.

The second neural network was a bigger fully connected neural network on which, the genetic algorithm was applied. The used network was a solution for the MNIST dataset resolution, with the architecture of [100, 50, 10] which gives the count of 160 neurons in the architecture.

2) Decomposition

For the first scenario, decomposition technique was the basic one, where neurons are added to the first thread, and the rest of the neurons of the studied architecture was added to the second thread. The second scenario is AG applied on ANN, and decomposition is represented by the selected element of the population.

[Table 2] gives the number of neurons affected to different threads, depending on the scenario and the available threads. the two first lines represent the two devices of the basic scenarios, as we can see the increment of the number of neurons in the first device and the inverse in the second one. The last three lines represents the three devices of the second scenario. As we can see number of neurons is affected randomly depending on the genetic algorithm's simples.

3) CPU Occupation

Figure 6. Processing Power Distribution.

Figure 6 represent different CPU verification during the decomposition process of the first scenario.

Figure 7. CPU OCCUPATION CHART.

Figure 7 shows the CPU verification during the decomposition process for the general scenario using AG. As we can see, the sum of the CPU occupation of the distributed architecture equals to the processing power needed for the centralized processing.

4. DISCUSSION

To evaluate the feasibility and effectiveness of distributing neural network computations across low-capacity devices, a simulation environment was developed using Python within Visual Studio 2019, executed on an Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-8550U CPU with 16GB of RAM. The use of Python facilitated straightforward implementation and manipulation of neural network structures. Notably, only the inference phase was considered, as pre-trained networks were employed to isolate computational distribution from the learning phase.

Two experimental scenarios were explored. The first involved a basic decomposition strategy applied to a small fully connected neural network with an architecture of [4, 5, 4, 3], using two threads to simulate two IoT devices. Neurons were distributed sequentially between the threads. The second, more advanced scenario used a larger network designed for the MNIST classification task ([100, 50, 10]) and applied a Genetic Algorithm (AG) to optimize the distribution of neurons across three simulated devices. In this case, neuron assignment was based on individuals within the genetic population, allowing for a more dynamic and potentially optimal decomposition.

The simulation setup does not model communication costs between devices, as all threads run on a single machine. However, the CPU usage of each thread during execution was monitored as a proxy for computational load.

Figures 6 and 7, along with **Table 2**, highlight how the workload was distributed. In the basic scenario, the neuron count across devices (threads) increased proportionally with CPU usage. In contrast, the AG-based decomposition resulted in a more irregular but optimized distribution, driven by the evolutionary selection process.

A critical insight from the experiments is that the **total CPU usage in the distributed setup equaled the CPU requirement of the centralized execution**. This confirms that the overhead introduced by decomposition and parallelization is negligible in terms of computational effort, and that the task is successfully partitioned without redundancy.

These findings demonstrate the **technical feasibility of distributing inference tasks** of neural networks across multiple low-resource devices, without loss of computational efficiency or accuracy. The approach allows small IoT devices to collaborate and collectively perform complex tasks that would otherwise exceed their individual capabilities. This could have significant implications for edge computing, particularly in environments with constrained infrastructure.

Future research will extend this methodology to other neural architectures (e.g., convolutional and recurrent networks), and address communication overhead, energy efficiency, and real-world network latency—factors that are crucial for practical deployment in IoT ecosystems.

5. CONCLUSION

In this work we presented the distribution technique for the small IOT devices Processing Power deployment. Different distribution techniques were studied in the literature and many challenges was faced. Our proposed methodology was given to overcomes these challenging points and proves that small IOT devices could collaborates to do bigger tasks and gives and identical results compared to the centralized processing. These results were proved by simulation using a fully connected neural network to sole the MNIST problem. result was promising and the technique is feasible in small IOT devices. Future work is going to be the application of this technique on different type of neural network architectures.

References

- [1] J. Hernavs, M. Ficko, L. Berus, R. Rudolf, and S. Klanc̃nik, “Deep learning in industry 4.0–brief overview,” Novi Sad, vol. 21, no. 2, p. 1, 2018.
- [2] A. Ghosh, D. Chakraborty, and A. Law, “Artificial intelligence in internet of things,” CAAI Transactions on Intelligence Technology, vol. 3, no. 4, pp. 208–218, 2018.
- [3] H. J. Vishnukumar, B. Butting, C. Mu¨ller, and E. Sax, “Machine learning and deep neural network—artificial intelligence core for lab and real-world test and validation for adas and autonomous vehicles: Ai for efficient and quality test and validation,” in 2017 Intelligent Systems Conference (IntelliSys). IEEE, 2017, pp. 714–721.
- [4] A. Poniszewska-Maranda and D. Kaczmarek, “Selected methods of artificial intelligence for internet of things conception,” in 2015 Federated Conference on Computer Science and Information Systems (FedCSIS). IEEE, 2015, pp. 1343–1348.
- [5] A. Ghis, K. Smiri, and A. Jemai, “Mixed software/hardware based neural network learning acceleration,” 2021.
- [6] F. Samie, L. Bauer, and J. Henkel, “From cloud down to things: An overview of machine learning in internet of things,” IEEE Internet of Things Journal, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 4921–4934, 2019.
- [7] S. Latif, Z. Zou, Z. Idrees, and J. Ahmad, “A novel attack detection scheme for the industrial internet of things using a lightweight random neural network,” IEEE Access, vol. 8, pp. 89 337–89 350, 2020.
- [8] W. Deng, X. Zhang, Y. Zhou, Y. Liu, X. Zhou, H. Chen, and H. Zhao, “An enhanced fast non-dominated solution sorting genetic algorithm for multi-objective problems,” Information Sciences, vol. 585, pp. 441–453, 2022.
- [9] A. J. Wilson, D. Pallavi, M. Ramachandran, S. Chinnasamy, and S. Sowmiya, “A review on memetic algorithms and its developments,” Electrical and Automation Engineering, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 7–12, 2022.
- [10] X. Liu and O. Baiocchi, “A comparison of the definitions for smart sensors, smart objects and things in iot,” in 2016 IEEE 7th Annual Information Technology, Electronics and Mobile Communication Conference (IEMCON). IEEE, 2016, pp. 1–4.
- [11] A. Al-Fuqaha, M. Guizani, M. Mohammadi, M. Aledhari, and M. Ayyash, “Internet of things: A survey on enabling technologies, protocols, and applications,” IEEE communications surveys & tutorials, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 2347–2376, 2015.
- [12] A. Poniszewska-Maranda and D. Kaczmarek, “Selected methods of artificial intelligence for internet of things conception,” in 2015 Federated Conference on Computer Science and Information Systems (FedCSIS). IEEE, 2015, pp. 1343–1348.
- [13] A. Glo´ria, F. Cercas, and N. Souto, “Comparison of communication protocols for low cost internet of things devices,” in 2017 South Eastern European Design Automation, Computer Engineering, Computer Networks and Social Media Conference (SEEDA- CECNSM). IEEE, 2017, pp. 1–6.

- [14] Y. Li and M. A. Thomas, "A multiple criteria decision analysis (mcda) software selection framework," in 2014 47th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences, 2014, pp. 1084–1094.
- [15] A. Guitouni and J.-M. Martel, "Tentative guidelines to help choosing an appropriate mcda method," *European journal of operational research*, vol. 109, no. 2, pp. 501–521, 1998.
- [16] S. Pedre, T. Krajník, E. Todorovich, and P. Borensztein, "A co-design methodology for processor-centric embedded systems with hardware acceleration using fpga," in 2012 VIII Southern Conference on Programmable Logic. IEEE, 2012, pp. 1–8.
- [17] I. Adamiec-Wojcik, K. Obrocki, and K. Warwas, "Distributed neural network used in control of brake torque distribution," in 2005 IEEE Intelligent Data Acquisition and Advanced Computing Systems: Technology and Applications. IEEE, 2005, pp. 116–119.
- [18] E. Di Pascale, I. Macaluso, A. Nag, M. Kelly, and L. Doyle, "The network as a computer: A framework for distributed computing over iot mesh networks," *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 5, no. 3, pp. 2107–2119, 2018.
- [19] S. Teerapittayanon, B. McDanel, and H.-T. Kung, "Distributed deep neural networks over the cloud, the edge and end devices," in 2017 IEEE 37th international conference on distributed computing systems (ICDCS). IEEE, 2017, pp. 328–339.
- [20] —, "Distributed deep neural networks over the cloud, the edge and end devices," in 2017 IEEE 37th international conference on distributed computing systems (ICDCS). IEEE, 2017, pp. 328–339.
- [21] H. Selvaraj, H. Niewiadomski, P. Buciak, M. Pleban, P. Sapiecha, T. Luba, and V. Muthukumar, "Implementation of large neural networks using decomposition," 2002.
- [22] R. J. Howlett and D. Lawrence, "A multi-computer neural network applied to machine-vision," in *Proceedings of ICNN'95- International Conference on Neural Networks*, vol. 2. IEEE, 1995, pp. 1150–1153.
- [23] J. Hernav, M. Ficko, L. Berus, R. Rudolf, and S. Klancnik, "Deep learning in industry 4.0—brief overview," *J. Prod. Eng.*, vol. 21, no. 2, pp. 1–5, 2018.
- [24] M. Cuka, D. Elmazi, R. Obukata, K. Ozero, T. Oda, and L. Barolli, "An integrated intelligent system for iot device selection and placement in opportunistic networks using fuzzy logic and genetic algorithm," in 2017 31st International Conference on Advanced Information Networking and Applications Workshops (WAINA). IEEE, 2017, pp. 201–207.

